

Preface

Welcome to the 1st International Conference on ASEAN Sustainable Development (ICASD 2023), a groundbreaking gathering of minds and visionaries dedicated to advancing the cause of sustainable development within the ASEAN region and beyond. Held on July 20-21, 2023, at the Crystal Hotel in the vibrant city of Hat Yai, Songkhla, Thailand.

Our world today faces an array of complex challenges, from environmental degradation and climate change to social inequality and economic instability. In response to these pressing issues, the United Nations introduced the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) as a global call to action to transform our world by 2030. With its theme, "Research and Social Innovation for Sustainable Development Goal: SDGs," ICASD 2023 is poised to serve as a critical platform for researchers, policymakers, practitioners, and activists to engage in robust dialogue, share innovative solutions, and forge collaborations that will drive progress toward these ambitious SDGs.

At ICASD 2023, we will explore the intersections of research and social innovation, recognizing that knowledge generation and practical implementation are two sides of the same coin in our journey toward sustainability. With a diverse array of keynote speakers, panel discussions, workshops, and presentations, participants will have the opportunity to delve into various facets of sustainable development, from environmental conservation and renewable energy to social justice, healthcare, and education. We extend our heartfelt gratitude to all the participants, organizers, sponsors, and partners who have come together to make ICASD 2023 a reality. Your commitment to sustainability and your dedication to turning research into action are the driving forces behind this event's success.

The conference created proceedings from the papers that participants submitted after committee members and international reviewers reviewed them. This volume intends to provide readers with the recent advances in sustainable development.

We look forward to the inspiring discussions, insights, and breakthroughs that will emerge from ICASD 2023 and the lasting impact they will have on our shared mission for sustainable development.

Assoc. Prof. Dr. Sompong O-Thong

Conference Chair

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